

Shannon's Entropy, Maximization and Large N Limit

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Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ where $P(i)$ is the probability of i is often shown to follow from the large N limit of a calculation of the $\ln(\text{arrangements})$ using factorials or in information theory from a large N scenario for which $NP(i)$ is the number of times an outcome i appears for large N . In this case overall Probability = $1/\text{number of arrangements}$. In both cases, there seems to be an argument for maximizing Shannon's entropy as it is linked to the number of arrangements.

In (1), we argued that one may obtain Shannon's entropy with no consideration of N or to arrangements, by seeking a function of $P(i)$ which changes as: $\sum_i f(P(i)) dP(i)$ just as dE thermal changes as $\sum_n e_i dP(e_n)$. In the case of entropy, i does not have to be e_n , it may be other variables such as p and x for a quantum eigenstate. The above consideration leads to $S = -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. There is, however, no reason for this quantity to be stationary if $P(i)$ is changed subject to $\sum_i dP(i) = 0$. If $\ln(P(i))$, however, is constant as in the case of fair coin or die, then S is automatically stationary i.e. $dS=0$ and one has: $P(i)=\text{constant}$. This may be formally obtained by maximizing S subject to $\sum_i P(i) = 1$. One may ask what happens in the case of a different constraint such as $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_n e_n P(e_n)$. There may be a number of $\{P(e_n)\}$ sets which yield the same E_{ave} , but different values of S . We argue that a stationary S is one for which small $dP(i)$ fluctuations do not change its value to first order and so this represents an equilibrium result. No use of large N is needed and no notion of arrangements. One still uses the idea of finding a stationary solution of S subject to constraints. This suggests that Shannon's entropy should hold in systems without large N and that one may maximize (find stationary solutions) in such a system subject to its constraints.

Large N Forms for Shannon's Entropy Derivation

It is often argued that a large N scenario is required to obtain Shannon's entropy. This large N scenario is ultimately linked to arrangements and so once Shannon's entropy is found it follows that one may maximize it in order to maximize the arrangements. Thus entropy becomes physically associated with a maximum number of arrangements.

In the case of direct arrangements:

$A = \ln\{ N! / \text{Product } i n_i! \}$ is simplified using Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) - N$ ((1))

If N is very large, the n_i are also assumed to be large and one has:

$A = \ln(N!) - \sum_i n_i \ln(n_i)$ with the first term being a constant which may be dropped, leaving Shannon's entropy.

For the case of information theory, one argues that for $P(i)$ the number of i outcomes for N large is: $NP(i)$ and so:

$$\ln(\text{Probability overall}) = \ln\left\{ \text{Product } i P(i)^{NP(i)} \right\} = \text{Sum over } i P(i)\ln(P(i))$$

((3))

Probability overall = 1 / (number of arrangements) so

$$\ln(\text{number of arrangements}) = - \text{Sum over } i P(i)\ln(P(i))$$

Both of these arguments above depend on large N and are linked to arrangements. Thus the physical idea seems to be to maximize the number of arrangements subject to whatever constraints are in the system.

We try to argue that large N is not needed and that one does not need the idea of arrangements.

Entropy from Different Considerations

In (1) we argued that one may try to find a statistical dot product which only depends on P(i) i.e. $C = \text{Sum over } i F(P(i))P(i)$, but changes as:

$$dC = \text{Sum over } i F(P(i)) dP(i) \quad ((4))$$

{F(P(i))} is of the form of a constant vector in i space for small dP(i) changes. This is analogous to dE thermal = $\text{Sum over } i e_i dP(e_i)$. A solution to this problem is:

$$C = \text{entropy } S = - \text{Sum over } i \ln(P(i)) P(i) \quad ((5))$$

Thus Shannon's entropy may be obtained without recourse to any arguments related to arrangements or large N. The next issue is to consider the maximization of this entropy.

Maximization of Entropy without the Notion of Arrangements

Consider ((5)) for the case of P(i)=constant which holds for a fair coin or die. In information theory it is argued that one needs a large N trial to test if indeed the coin or die is fair, but given the a priori result that it is constructed in a fair manner, there is no need for large N to enter the discussion. (It is just used to confirm fairness.) If P(i)=constant then $\text{Sum over } i dP(i) = 0$ so:

$$dS = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Thus P(i)=constant, in other words there is no preference of any i, or there is a complete loss of bias towards any i, as well as a stationary S. Formally, one may obtain this result by maximizing S subject to $\text{Sum over } i P(i)$.

A question arises: What does one do in the case of a different constraint, e.g. $\text{Sum over } i e_i P(i) = \text{Eave}$? There may be various sets of { P(i) } which all yield the same Eave. There is no argument in this situation regarding maximizing arrangements so at first it might seem that any

set $\{P(i)\}$ which satisfies the constraint is fine. The idea, however, that constant probabilities lead to a stationary S may be a hint that a stationary S is preferred. In fact, if one has a special set of $\{P(i)\}$ which satisfies the constraint and makes S stationary, then small fluctuations will not lead to a first order change in S . In other words S is stable against small changes which is an indication of equilibrium. Otherwise S would be changing continually from one value to another as changes occurred leading to from one $\{P(i)\}$ set to another.

Thus we argue that one does not need to associate the idea of a stationary (or maximum) entropy with that of a maximum number of arrangements. We argue that this becomes important for small systems. If one takes the idea of arrangements seriously, then for small N systems, one might try to calculate exactly $\ln(N!/n_1!n_2!n_3!)$ where $n_1+n_2+n_3=N$ (etc) and then obtain an expression for entropy without using Stirling's approximation. The approach here suggests that Shannon's form holds even for small systems because it is linked to finding a dot product $\sum_i F(P(i)) P(i)$ which changes as: $\sum_i F(P(i)) dP(i)$, in other words there is a vector $F(P(i))$ which is constant in i space for small $dP(i)$ changes. Furthermore we argue that one wishes to maximize the dot product subject to constraints in the system.

Conclusion

We try to argue that the idea of arrangements and large N are not needed to obtain Shannon's entropy, even though they are usually employed. In particular, this becomes a consideration if one calculates the number of arrangements using factorials. For a small N system, instead of using Stirling's formula, this would imply one keep the factorial functions leading to a result different from Shannon's entropy. Furthermore we argue that using the idea of arrangements leads to a biased view of maximizing arrangements to find entropy.

We argue (as in (1)) that one may obtain Shannon's entropy by assuming a dot product: $S = -\sum_i F(P(i)) P(i)$ such that: $dS = -\sum_i F(P(i)) dP(i)$. $F(P(i))$ plays the role of a constant vector in i space for small $dP(i)$. (This is similar to the situation of $dE_{\text{thermal}} = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$.) This view leads to Shannon's form $S = -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ without any need for arrangements or large N as shown in (1). Furthermore, if $P(i) = \text{constant}$ (e.g. a fair coin or die) then $dS=0$ i.e. is stationary. Formally this is the same as maximizing S subject to the constraint $\sum_i P(i)=1$. If one has other constraints, e.g. $\sum_i e_i P(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$, then one might suggest a similar maximization. This makes no use of the idea of the maximization of arrangements. A set of $P(e_i)$ which maximizes (or makes stationary) S means that for small changes to $P(e_i)$, S does not change to first order and so it has the appearance of an equilibrium quantity.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Bound Information $\ln(WW)$, $\ln(a(p)a(p))$ as Statistical Constant Vectors over Variables x,p ? (preprint, zenodo, 2022)